

Corrective Support in the Context of Psychological Assistance to Children with Psychophysical Disorders

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Abstract: *The relevance of our research is due to the need to improve the system of training specialists in the field of special psychology, due to the fact that the applied tasks of special psychology is the training of highly qualified and competitive specialists to work with persons with psychophysical disorders. This will positively affect the quality of their future professional activities in correctional support in educational and rehabilitation institutions, especially in the conditions of the transition period to inclusive education.*

The leading place in the system of psychological assistance to children with psychophysical disabilities is occupied by psycho-correctional support, especially in the context of the transition of modern special education to social integration and inclusive education of persons with psychophysical disabilities. The effectiveness of psycho-correctional support will depend on the psychological readiness of future psychologists for professional interaction with this category of people. First of all, the immediate tasks of psychological correctional support for children with psychophysical disabilities are their psychosocial adaptation. At the stage of integration of a child with mental and physical disabilities through inclusion in the circle of peers with a normal level of development, the psychological support of families who upbringing such children is also especially important. The stimulating function of a professional orientation, which ensures professional and personal stability, is clearly actualized during corrective support for children with psychophysical disabilities, regardless of the negative impact of external factors.

Keywords: *special psychology, psychophysical disorders, training, rehabilitation institutions, inclusive education, future psychologists, psychosocial adaptation.*

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Introduction

The UN Declaration on Social Development proclaimed new conceptual principles that emphasize the need for the development of modern society based on tolerance, forbearance, condemnation of discrimination, respect for personal identity, equality of opportunities, etc. These provisions are the basis of the main goal of social development - the creation of such a society that will be able to provide protection and full integration into society of all segments of the population, including persons with disabilities. Such integration into society opens the way for the realization of rights and opportunities for the above-mentioned persons on an equal basis with healthy people.

Since the 90s, the theory of inclusion - inclusion has been defined as the leading model of modern public and social relations towards persons with disabilities, in particular, towards children with psychophysical disabilities (Arkes H.R., 1982; А.Андрєс (2000), Stroianovska O., 2020; Sheremet, 2019; Behas, 2019; Bezliudnyi, 2019; et al.). This theory is based on the recognition and respect of individual human differences, and also assumes the preservation of the relative autonomy of each social group, and the ideas and style of behavior that inherent in the traditionally dominant group have to be modified based on the pluralism of customs and opinions (Bondar V.I., 2007). The focus of this model of social behavior is autonomy, participation in social activities, the creation of a system of social binds and the acceptance of each individual by society without restrictions.

At the present stage of development, society has come to recognize and affirm the right of persons with psychophysical development to full participation in public life and tries to realize the need to create conditions for the full realization of this right, A.A. Kolupaeva (2007). M.K. Sheremet (2007) believes that against the background of international discussions on topical problems of education and upbringing of children with psychophysical disorders, the acute and first of all the task is to "improve the quality of psychological and pedagogical assistance to this category of children, create services for early detection and early assistance (early intervention), ensuring inclusive education, organizing and training specialists who will work in new conditions and in a new system of values ". Accordingly, today there is an urgent need for highly professional and competent specialists who are able to ensure the full social adaptation of such persons, to promote their integration into society by introducing an early intervention system and inclusive education. In difficult public and

social realities, a child with impaired psychophysical development vitally needs psychocorrectional support from an educated specialist.

The relevance of our research is due to the need to improve the system of training specialists in the field of special psychology, due to the fact that the applied tasks of special psychology is the training of highly qualified and competitive specialists to work with persons with psychophysical disorders. This will positively affect the quality of their future professional activities in correctional support in educational and rehabilitation institutions, especially in the conditions of the transition period to inclusive education.

In modern conditions, the increase in the status and role of specialists in the field of special psychology is largely determined by the level of their professional competence. For the convenience of presenting the results of the study, we consider it necessary to call such specialists as *special psychologists*, although such a specialty is not indicated in the State Classifier of Professions of Ukraine. In Ukraine, only the Institute of Correctional Pedagogy and Psychology of the National Pedagogical University named after MP Drahomanov has been training a special psychologist since 2005. The main task of his professional activity is to conduct screening diagnostics and differential diagnosis of children both in secondary schools and in special educational and rehabilitation institutions in order to identify the current level of psychophysical abilities of the child, their specifics and make a forecast for further development. Also an increase in a person's mental resources, his adaptive capabilities, aimed at harmonizing mental development, health protection, overcoming ailments and psychological rehabilitation. Currently, at the stage of Ukraine's formation as a state of the European level, an acute problem is to improve the system of training special psychologists in order to increase the level of their professional orientation, since for a long time the educational and rehabilitation system of Ukraine, which served people with mental and physical disabilities, was provided by workers who did not always have had the appropriate specialized vocational training. It is clear that this negatively affected the quality and efficiency of the correctional and rehabilitation process. Today the social need for the development of initiative, creative, business qualities of special psychologists is acutely aware, which involves strengthening the creative components of their training. A modern specialist in the field of special psychology needs new conceptual thinking, which will encourage him to contemplate the processes of mental ontogenesis and dysontogenesis, socialization and education of persons with psychophysical disorders and will provide a high quality of professional activity.

Psychological assistance to children with developmental problems as an important link in the system of their habilitation and rehabilitation

Psychological assistance to children with developmental problems as an important link in the system of their habilitation and rehabilitation. In modern conditions, the psychological support of the educational process in correctional education and rehabilitation institutions becomes especially important. Such prominent scientists as V.I. Bondar (2007), L.M. Grechko (2008) and others draw the community's attention to this. I.I. Mamaichuk (2001) considers psychological assistance to children with psychophysical disabilities as a complex system of psychological and rehabilitation influences which aimed at increasing social activity, developing independence, strengthening the social position of the personality of a child with developmental disabilities, the formation of a system of value attitudes and orientation, development intellectual processes that correspond to the mental and physical capabilities of the child. This complex multi-level system includes not only psycho-correctional and psycho-counseling work, but also psychological follow-up, psychological support, psychological prognostics aimed at effort both for the child and for his family as a whole and her social environment.

The main goal of psychological assistance to children with psychophysical disabilities is the harmonization of their personal and intellectual potential, correction of existing disorders in mental development, prevention of possible developmental deviations caused by both the internal specifics of mental dysontogenesis and external conditions. It is important to solve such problems as the elimination of secondary personal reactions to an existing mental or physical defect, an inadequate style of family education, hospitalism, etc. (Mamaichuk, 2001). In other words, psychological assistance to a disabled child should contribute to the development of such a child as a participant in a complex social space and ensure his readiness and the ability to live among people of different social communities, freely, actively and fully realizing himself.

An important part of psychological assistance to children and adolescents with developmental problems is psychological correctional support. There are many approaches to understanding this concept, and the question of the need for psychological support within the psychotherapy, age-related psychological counseling, family counseling, medical psychology, etc. is also relevant. Analysis of the literature allows us to highlight the following areas of its study. Psychological support is considered as a determinant of personality development in culture (Brushlinsky 1991;

Vygotsky 1982); as emotional and moral support (Rogers, 1984; Soloviov, 2010); as an element of psychosocial assistance (Ailamazyan, 1999; Abramova, 2000), etc. According to the research of T.O. Bozhenko (2009) in the scientific literature, psychological support is understood as a certain system of scientifically based means and methods which lead to self-determination of the individual in the process of forming his abilities, value orientations and self-awareness. The implementation of psychological support occurs due to the optimization of the psychological state of a person in the development process due to the complete solution or decrease in the relevance of psychological problems that impede the process of socialization and self-realization at each stage of the life path.

Psychological support according to the Law of Ukraine "On Rehabilitation of the Disabled in Ukraine" (№ 3235-IV of December 20, 2005) (<http://zakon.rada.gov.ua/cgi-bin/laws/main.cgi?page=2&nreg=2961-15>, 2005) – it is "a system of socio-psychological, psychological and pedagogical means and methods of helping a person in order to optimize her psycho-emotional state in the process of forming abilities and self-awareness, promoting social and professional self-determination, increasing competitiveness in the labor market and direction a person's efforts to the realization of their own professional career ". According to the "Regulations on vocational guidance and psychological support of the population in the Russian Federation" (www.humanities.edu.ru/db/msg/56885, 1996) psychological support is carried out by optimizing the psychological state of a person as a result of the complete resolution or reduction of the topicality of psychological problems, that prevent labor, professional, social self-realization at each stage of life of an individual, small groups, groups, formal and informal associations of people.

The main areas of psychological support are: 1) psychological prevention - promoting the full mental development of the individual, small and large groups, prevention of possible personal and interpersonal problems of ill-being and socio-psychological conflicts, including the development of recommendations for improving the socio-psychological conditions for self-realization of the individual, small groups and collectives, taking into account the existing socio-economic relations; 2) psychological counseling - providing assistance to the individual in his self-knowledge, adequate self-esteem and adaptation in real life, the formation of the value-motivational sphere, overcoming crisis situations and achieving emotional stability, contributes to continuous personal growth and self-development; 3) psychological correction - an active psychological and pedagogical

influence aimed at overcoming deviations in mental and personal development, harmonization of personality and interpersonal relations.

In modern society, psychological support is carried out in order to provide psychological support for the free and harmonious development of the personality at all stages of its formation and self-realization; preventing the development of negative trends in human psychology, overcoming the difficulties of personal growth, correcting behavior disorders, overcoming conflict situations in relationships. The main methods of psychological support include psychological education; psychological and psychotherapeutic counseling; psychological diagnosis; psychological training; psychological correction and other individual and group methods of psychological work.

In modern science, the following leading directions of psychological support can be distinguished which based on an understanding of its content: social adaptation, which includes adaptation to reality, the development of the ability to control one's life under various circumstances, both favorable and unfavorable (B. Lenner-Axelson 1995); determination together with the child of his own interests and goals, opportunities and ways to overcome obstacles that prevent him from maintaining his own human dignity and independently achieving the desired results in self-education, communication, lifestyle (A.G. Asmolov 1983, I.D. Bekh 2003, O.S. Gazman 1995, et al.); support of the individual in the learning process, based on the stimulation of cognitive activity, determining opportunities to independently achieve the desired results in learning (O.S. Gazman 1995, A.A. Kolupaeva 2007, et al.); socialization and personal growth, which provide for further favorable social and personal development (K. McLaughlin 2013, et al.); assistance in the formation and development of personality, self-realization and self-actualization (A.G. Asmolov 1983, I.S. Bulakh 2003, S.D. Maksimenko 2003, et al.).

Psychological correctional support for children with mental and physical disabilities

At the stage of integration of a child with mental and physical disabilities through inclusion in the circle of peers with a normal level of development, the psychological support of families who upbringing such children is also especially important. We consider it necessary to disclose in more detail these leading tasks of psycho-correctional support.

An urgent problem of education and upbringing of children with psychophysical disabilities is their integration into society in accordance with

certain international legislative documents and laws of Ukraine (UN Convention "On the Rights of the Child", Universal Declaration "Education for All", Salaman Declaration, UN Convention on Persons with special needs, the Law of Ukraine "On Education", "On Child Protection", "On the Basics of Social Protection of Disabled People in Ukraine", "On the Rehabilitation of Disabled People in Ukraine", etc.), as well as the rights of every child to life, protection, education, etc. But, as modern leading scientists in the field of defectology note, in the system of domestic special education today, the equality of the rights to education of persons with psychophysical disabilities is not fully satisfied, and existing educational services often do not correspond to the needs, personal and social needs of such persons (V.I. Bondar 2007, V.V. Zasenکو 2007, A.A. Kolupaeva 2007, et al.) Taking this into account, modern correctional education is faced with the task of improving and developing new social and educational areas, among which inclusive education is promising.

The problem of integration and socialization of persons with psychophysical disabilities and the issues of inclusion in education have been studied by many scientists: V.I. Bondar (2007), V.V. Zasenکو (2007), Yu.M. Naida (2008), L.M. Shipitsina (2004) and others.

Inclusive education is a form of social integration. According to the conclusion of N.Z. Sofyi (2007) and Yu.M. Naida (2008), inclusive education is a system of educational services that is based on the principle of ensuring the fundamental right of children to education, and also differentiates the educational process, responding to the needs of students of all groups and categories, including children with psychophysical disabilities in general educational institutions. In any form, inclusive education provides for the mandatory guidance of both a teacher-defectologist and the direct participation of a special psychologist, because in order to include children with psychophysical disabilities in the educational process with groups of healthy peers, it requires early diagnosis, special training, maximum correctional psychological and pedagogical support, parental assistance, as well as appropriate equipment and special methods of rehabilitation. The integration of children into a team of healthy peers contributes to their socialization, mastering the skills necessary for life in society. Healthy children also gain new experiences: they learn to understand and accept other people, to empathize with children who have problems, to help them overcome difficulties.

Based on the research on inclusive education, L.M. Grechko (2008) formulated criteria for assessing the possibility of a child with psychophysical disabilities staying in a general education school, namely: the

child should feel comfortable and not be limited in satisfaction of their social and personal needs; the child must study according to the program available to him; the institution must ensure the optimal psychophysical development of the child; the institution must organize comprehensive psychological, medical and special pedagogical assistance to the child, aimed at eliminating or reducing the deficiency of psychophysical disabilities and preventing the occurrence of secondary and tertiary defects.

In our opinion, focusing on the study of inclusive education AA Kolupaeva (2007), psychological correctional support for children with mental and physical disabilities should focus on the following principles: guaranteed psycho-correctional support and rehabilitation assistance for children with mental and physical disabilities and their families; accessibility and equal rights of children to early support and education, regardless of the degree of disability, age, social status, etc.; individual approach to each child and differentiation of the provision of psycho-correctional support; cooperation of a family that is upbringing a child and specialists providing psychological correctional support.

We agree with the opinion of II Mamaychuk (2001) that in working with such children, psychological correctional support should be provided in two main areas: first, it is the support of children and adolescents with developmental disabilities, and secondly, the support of parents and the immediate environment of such children. We consider psychological correctional support of parents and the entourage of a child with psychophysical disabilities as a system of measures aimed at reducing emotional discomfort in connection with the child's illness and the need to interact with such a child; strengthening confidence in the child's abilities; formation of an adequate attitude to the problems of the child; estimating adequate relationships and styles of family education.

In our opinion, considering the correctional support of children with psychophysical disabilities, it is important to note that all nosological groups of disorders in psychophysical development have common regularity of mental development. This statement was put forward by famous scientists such as V.I. Lubovsky (2005), V.M. Sorokin (2003), O.M. Usanova (2006) and others. The main ones are: reduction of the level of development (cognitive, personal, speech, motor, etc.); deformation of the social situation of development; difficulties of social adaptation; changes in personality development; reduction of tolerance to external stressors; limited compensatory personal and behavioral capabilities; violation of communication; slowing down the consolidation of life experience; the

presence of potential development opportunities, but subject to the possibility of improving functions to a certain level; decreased activity, etc..

In the process of psychological correctional support for children with psychophysical disabilities, assistance is provided in compensating for existing deficiencies of psychophysical development, as well as in the formation of adequate self-esteem, the level of ambitions, communication skills, in overcoming personality disorders and disorders of the emotional sphere, etc. That is, psychological correctional support is an integral part of the process of socialization of children with psychophysical developmental disorders, their integration into society, especially at the stage of inclusive education among peers with normal development. Psychological correctional support should provide children with psychophysical disabilities with conditions for overcoming and compensating for disabilities and should be aimed at creating opportunities for them to participate in the life of society, equal with other citizens.

The process of implementation of psychological correctional support is long and requires a mandatory comprehensive approach, involving all professionals working with the child: a special psychologist, special education teacher, doctor, social worker, etc. However, the main role in this process belongs to the psychologist, who, depending on the existing problems, develops specific measures aimed at psychological correctional support for children with psychophysical disorders and their parents. The effectiveness of psychological correctional support largely depends not only on the level of professional qualification of the psychologist, but also on his personal characteristics (Yefimova S. 2002; Zabramnaya S. 2004).

Now in Ukraine, a purposeful search is underway for ways to include children with psychophysical disabilities in the institutions of the general education system. As domestic scientists note, the relevance and significance of this work is very important, since psychological correctional support and rehabilitation of children with psychophysical developmental disorders, the creation of conditions for their successful social and psychophysiological adaptation, the development of their vital competence is a fundamental sign of democratic education and public life (V.I. Bondar 2007, V.V. Zasenکو 2007, M.K. Sheremet 2007, et al.)

Conclusions

In the system of psychological assistance to children with psychophysical disabilities, psycho-correctional support occupies a leading place, especially in the context of the transition period of modern special

education to social integration and inclusive education of persons with psychophysical disabilities. The effectiveness of psycho-correctional support will depend on the psychological readiness of future psychologists for professional interactions with this category of persons. First of all, the tasks at hand of psychological correctional support for children with psychophysical disabilities are their psychosocial adaptation. Psychological support for families upbringing such children is also important, especially at the stage of integration of a child with psychophysical disabilities through inclusion in the circle of peers with a normal level of development. When providing correctional support to children with psychophysical disabilities, the stimulating function of a professional orientation is clearly updated, which ensures professional and personal stability regardless of the negative impact of external factors and also determines its leading role in training psychologists to work with the above category of children.

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